

THE IMPACT OF THE WAR BETWEEN RUSSIA AND UKRAINE ON THE ATTITUDES OF THE INHABITANTS REGARDING TOURIST TRIPS: THE CASE OF BOSNIA AND HERZEGOVINA

Amra ČAUŠEVIĆ^{A*}

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Abstract

With the first days of the war, the first consequences of the war events in Ukraine on tourism and all other trips in Europe, Asia, and the whole world began to appear. The purpose of this study is to investigate the impact of the war between Russia and Ukraine on the attitudes of the inhabitants of Bosnia and Herzegovina regarding travel, i.e., it will be analyzed whether socio-demographic factors have an impact on the intention to travel in 2022, which tourist destinations do the inhabitants of Bosnia and Herzegovina perceived as safer, where they intend to travel and by which means of transport. The convenience sample included 265 respondents (residents of Bosnia and Herzegovina). The research was conducted from March 2nd, 2022 until May 17th, 2022. To collect primary data, an online questionnaire using Google Forms was used, the link of which was distributed electronically, via e-mail, and through the Facebook social network.

Key words

War, Tourist trips, Attitudes, Russian Federation, Ukraine

INTRODUCTION

With the first days of the war, the first consequences of the war events in Ukraine on tourism and all other trips in Europe, Asia, and the whole world began to appear. At the beginning of the war, air traffic to and from Ukraine was disrupted, and then completely stopped. A large number of Western countries have imposed numerous sanctions on the Russian Federation in terms of its economic, traffic, financial, and trade blockade. So far, thirty-six countries have banned the landing and overflight of Russian planes, covering all of Central and Western Europe, Great Britain, New Zealand, Canada, and the United States. As a countermeasure, Russia introduced the same bans for flights of airlines from those parts of the world to Russia. From the above, it can be concluded that in the coming period, Russia and Ukraine will not function as emitting, but also as receptive tourist markets. Most tourists in Europe

A* University of Sarajevo, Department of Geography, Faculty of Science,
Bosnia and Herzegovina

 <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9657-4049>

e-mail: amra.causevic@pmf.unsa.ba (corresponding author)

use cars as a means of transport for tourist trips, and it is evident that car destinations have an absolute advantage over air destinations. In addition to insecurity, the war in Ukraine has brought about an increase in the cost of living. Inflationary trends are under great pressure, and food and energy prices are constantly rising. Cost rates rise above the increase in income rates. This is an unfavorable situation, both for tourists and providers of tourist services. The estimates in June 2022 showed that inflation in Bosnia and Herzegovina amounted to 14% (Aljazeera, 2023).

OBJECTIVES

In the context of the current situation of the war between Russia and Ukraine, this article will analyze whether socio-demographic factors have an impact on the intention to travel in 2022, which tourist destinations the inhabitants of Bosnia and Herzegovina consider safe, where they intend to travel and by which means of transport.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Security has generally posed a challenge to those who have attempted to reach an ideal, comprehensive and encompassing definition of the concept. Orthodox perspectives have mainly focused on the state as a “harbinger” of security that defends its territory and citizens against external enemies through the acquisition of military grade weapons. Neorealist theorist, Stephen Walt defines security as “the study of threat, use, and control of military force”. Since security is a seemingly self-explanatory concept, it has also been rather underdeveloped to the point that International Relations theorist Barry Buzan argues that before the ‘80s, “conceptual literature on security” was rather neglected if not, a sorely absent field of inquiry. Buzan himself, along with Ole Wæver and Jaap de Wilde, proposed a new research agenda for security as evidenced in the book: “Security: A New Framework for Analysis”. These authors are regarded as the main representatives of what today we refer to as the Copenhagen School of Security Studies (Filimon, 2016:47).

Safety is one of the basic human needs all over the world. After creating the conditions for fulfilling the existential needs, this is our most important need according to accepted human norms (Maslow, 1943). Tourism represents an important economic component that is constantly developing (Nurković and Rewucki, 2018; Dehoorne, Mihaela Olau and Tudor, 2019). So it is very important that the destination is perceived as safe (Herman et al., 2022; Michalek, 2022). Today, tourism is increasingly controlled and under the influence of security reasons. Travelers consider it important that the chosen destination, the target country or area, the roads leading there, as well as the means of travel are safe. Although the security issue of tourism is not a new social challenge because tourism has always assumed some kind of risk factor (Michalkó, 2004; Bujdosó and Györki, 2011), the

terrorist acts and armed conflicts are becoming more frequent nowadays, so this issue is of utmost importance for everyday life to solve in both the developed and underdeveloped countries. Today, communication means allow us to immediately receive such news, which usually causes fear, anxiety, and indecision not only among the local population but also among a much wider audience (Sass, 2020).

After the tragic terrorist attacks of September 11th, a group of researchers began to study security problems; moreover, these problems have become a special field of research in tourism (Kóvári and Zimányi, 2011, Sass, 2020). Sobotova, Havlicek and Klingorova (2019) analyzed the causes of the fear of Islam and explain Islamophobia in two socially and geographically distinct contexts: in Czechia and in Spain. Several articles have examined the impact of terrorism on tourism (Dávid et al., 2007; Varga and Bagdi, 2011; Gaydukevich, 2017). Gaydukevich (2017) claims that these events have an extremely negative impact both on the economy of the affected countries and on the tourism industry throughout the world (Sass, 2020).

Sass (2020) believes that the following factors make the events unique: the country where the terrorist attack took place, a political, geopolitical conflict, or a war that lasts for years. Events that assume a security risk causes an immediate reaction from travelers as most tourists in the territory to decide to return home, and this can cause a wave of canceling the previously booked trips (Dávid et al., 2007).

There are many studies related to the relationship between tourism and terrorism in different countries or regions (Pizam, 1999; Goodrich, 2002; Pizam and Fleischer, 2002; Chu, 2008).

Terrorist disasters affect world travel, while bombings in many places have an immediate impact on tourism, although most destinations eventually recover lost trade over time. Perceptions of travel may change as a result of the frequency and perceived scale of terrorist attacks reported in the media. Some destinations may be associated with greater travel risks than others, such as; the events in the USA since September 11th, 2001, the Bali bombings in 2002 and 2005, the Madrid bombings in 2004, the incidents in Turkey and Egypt in 2005 and the attacks on London's transportation system in 2005. All of these led to a perceived increased risk of terrorism in the international tourism scene and led to short-term cancellations by travelers with high-risk sensitivity (Ingram, Tabari and Watthanakhomprathip, 2013). The armed civil conflict that took place on the island of Sri Lanka from 1983 to 2009 certainly led to a drop in tourist arrivals, especially in the later stages when certain countries issued a warning to citizens not to travel to that country (Buultjens, Ratnayake, and Gnanapala, 2015). It is also the same case with Lebanon, where political instability affects the planning and development of tourism (Issa and Altinay, 2006).

Goodrich (2002) used the 9/11 terrorist attack as a case study and analyzed its impact on the US tourism industry. Pizam and Fleischer (2002), as well as Pizam (1999), concluded that terrorism resulted in a high frequency of attacks, but

regardless of the degree of severity, it had a much greater negative impact on tourism demand than high severity, but low frequency. If terrorist attacks happen frequently and no matter how serious they are, tourism demand will gradually decline and eventually enter an era of stagnation. This is the result of data on tourism demand in Israel between May 1991 and May 2001 (Mao, 2019). Chu (2008) attempted to forecast tourism demand using the fractionally integrated ARMA model and the Asian financial crisis as well as the 9/11 terrorist attack as examples of economic and political shocks. Athanasopoulos and Hyndman (2008) used a regression framework to identify the impact of the 2000 Sydney Olympics and the 2002 Bali bombings on domestic tourism demand in Australia. They found that the Sydney Olympics promoted immediate demand for business travel, while the number of visitors meeting friends and relatives increased significantly after the Bali explosion (Mao, 2019).

Richter and Waugh (1986) were the first to explore the relationship between the two and believed that tourism and terrorism were logical companions. The economic and political impact of terrorism on tourism was assessed, including the sensitivity of the tourism industry to general political conflicts and the vulnerability of travelers and tourist facilities to terrorist activities (Mao, 2019). Some researchers believe that there is a long-term relationship between them (Gil-Alana et al., 2015). Gil-Alana et al. (2015) found that there is a lasting impact of crisis events on most Croatian coastal towns using both parametric and semi-parametric approaches to fractional integration (Mao, 2019).

There is extensive literature that deals with different types of political shocks and their impacts on the tourism and hospitality sector. Hall and O'Sullivan (1996) note that perceptions of political instability and security serve as a precondition for tourists' decisions to travel or not to travel to a given destination. One of the most famous and influential is Neumayer's (2004) research, which showed that tourism arrivals decline due to a number of different unattractive political factors (human rights violations, conflicts, etc., as well as political/violent events). These findings confirm what many would expect, namely that tourists avoid unpleasant political situations. Llorca-Vivero (2008) in their research that included over 130 tourist destinations found support for Neumayer's (2004) research. In addition, Edgell et al. (2008) claim that if there is no security at the destination, business, and all other travel will be negatively affected. An example is the terrorist bombings in Bali in 2005, which dramatically affected tourism revenues in the short term. All in all, the aforementioned studies (Neumayer, 2004; Llorca-Vivero, 2008) empirically illustrate that destinations that are unattractive due to their political attributes will be largely avoided by travelers (Ivanov, Gavrulina, Webster and Ralko, 2017).

One of the direct consequences of the war is its effect on the sustainable development and stability of the country, and the automatic lack of these factors directly affects the tourism industry. Tourists are the first group to leave war zones

before any other people, because when there is no safe place to live how can they be expected to stay in a dangerous and unsafe place. When a country has no tourists due to an armed conflict, many local businesses will disappear. Thus, armed conflicts always have direct and indirect destructive effects on the socio-economic situation of the countries involved in them (Sharifi Tarazkohi and Makan Sedaghat, 2014).

Experts believe that war is the most terrible poison for the tourism industry. The tourism industry itself brings sustainable development and stability. One of the key effective elements in modern armed conflicts is the significant time and resources spent on modernizing military weapons to control battlefields. Tourists never come to places that are covered with mines. Also, they never go to places that are at risk of aerial bombardment by warring parties (Sharifi Tarazkohi and Makan Sedaghat, 2014).

Sudden street protests, social unrest, civil war, acts of terrorism, visible violations of human rights, and even the very threat of such problems can cause tourists to change their travel plans (Tomczewska-Popowycz and Quirini-Popławski, 2021). The tourism sector is extremely dependent on stability, peace, and security (Al-Hamarneh and Steiner, 2004). Although the war, political instability, and tourism in Ukraine have been the subject of numerous studies, it is still not enough. Pandey and Kumar (2022) examined the impacts of the Russia-Ukraine war 2022 on the global tourism sector stocks. Levytska, Klymchuk, Shestakova and Biletska (2023) analyzed the tourist potential of Ukraine, that is, challenges and prospects of the post-war time. Ukraine and its tourism sector suffered the most in the war, and since the prospects for the end of the war are very uncertain, the question arises of preserving the country's tourist potential, finding ways for its faster recovery and post-war development.

In order to fill the gaps in the existing literature, this article explores the consequences of the war between Ukraine and Russia on the attitudes of the inhabitants of Bosnia and Herzegovina regarding tourist travel. An attempt will be made to find a connection between the war and the intention to travel, the means of transport for these purposes, and the respondents' attitudes about safe tourist destinations.

DATA AND METHODS

The subject of this article is the analysis of the impact of the war between Russia and Ukraine on the attitudes of the inhabitants of Bosnia and Herzegovina regarding tourist trips. The main research questions raised in the research are:

- Do socio-demographic factors influence the intention to travel in 2022 in the context of the current situation of the war between Russia and Ukraine?
- Which tourist destinations do the inhabitants of Bosnia and Herzegovina perceived as safer during the current war situation between Russia and Ukraine?

- Where do the people of Bosnia and Herzegovina intend to travel in the context of the current war situation between Russia and Ukraine?
- What means of transport will be used for tourist trips in the context of the current war situation between Russia and Ukraine?

The study used a quantitative approach to research that included data collection through a survey. To collect primary data, an online questionnaire using Google Forms was used, the link of which was distributed electronically, via e-mail, and through a social network (Facebook). The convenience sample included 265 respondents (residents of Bosnia and Herzegovina). The research was conducted from March 2nd, 2022 to May, 17th, 2022.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive statistics and tests of statistical significance were used in the analysis and interpretation of the obtained data. Statistical tests are selected according to the type of data processed in the analysis. Descriptive statistics were used to describe the research results by variables and as a basis for statistical tests. The Mann-Whitney U test was chosen for the analysis because the data does not have a normal distribution; represents ordinal variables, to prove the relationship between two variables (Čaušević, Mirić, Drešković & Hrelja, 2020). Kruskal-Wallis is a non-parametric test that was chosen in the analysis because we have 3 or more independent samples and the test is based on rank.

Fig. 1 Where do you intend to travel in 2022 in the context of the current war situation between Ukraine and Russia?

Source: Research results, 2022.

Fig. 1 shows that, during 2022, and in the context of the war in Ukraine, the largest percentage of respondents intend to travel throughout Europe (23.4%) and to Bosnia and Herzegovina (21.5%) and Croatia (20.8%).

The following figures show where the respondents intend to travel considering the war in Ukraine and different socio-demographic factors.

Fig. 2 Intention to travel in 2022 in the context of the current war situation between Ukraine and Russia and gender as a sociodemographic factor

Source: Research results, 2022.

Fig. 2 shows that, in the context of the war in Ukraine, the largest percentage of men want to travel in Bosnia and Herzegovina (28.7%), Europe (27.7%), and Croatia (20.8%), while the largest percentage of women want to travel in Europe (21.1%), Croatia (20.5%) and Bosnia and Herzegovina (17.5%).

Fig. 3 shows that, in the context of the war in Ukraine, the largest percentage of respondents older than 50 years want to travel to Croatia, while the largest percentage of respondents aged 31-50 want to travel to Europe and Croatia, and the largest percentage of respondents aged 18 to 30 want to travel in Europe and Bosnia and Herzegovina.

Fig. 4 shows that, in the context of the war in Ukraine, the largest percentage of respondents with postgraduate studies want to travel to Croatia and Europe, while the largest percentage of respondents with a university degree want to travel to Europe, Croatia, and Bosnia and Herzegovina, and the largest percentage of respondents with high school education want to travel throughout Bosnia and Herzegovina, and Europe and Croatia.

Fig. 3 Intention to travel in 2022 in the context of the current war situation between Ukraine and Russia and age as a sociodemographic factor

Source: Research results, 2022.

Fig. 4 Intention to travel in 2022 in the context of the current war situation between Ukraine and Russia and level of education as a sociodemographic factor

Source: Research results, 2022.

Fig. 5 shows that, in the context of the war in Ukraine, the largest percentage of pensioners want to travel to Bosnia and Herzegovina, while the largest percentage of students want to travel to Europe, and the largest percentage of respondents who are employed want to travel in Europe, as well as in Croatia and Bosnia and Herzegovina.

Fig. 5 Intention to travel in 2022 in the context of the current war situation between Ukraine and Russia and employment status as a sociodemographic factor
Source: Research results, 2022.

Fig. 6 Intention to travel in 2022 in the context of the current war situation between Ukraine and Russia and a monthly income as a sociodemographic factor
Source: Research results, 2022.

Fig. 6 shows that, in the context of the war in Ukraine, the largest percentage of respondents with monthly incomes below 500 BAM (50.0%), and those with monthly incomes between 500 BAM and 1,500 BAM want to travel to Bosnia and

Herzegovina, while the largest percentage with monthly incomes of 1,500 BAM up to 2,500 BAM want to travel in Europe, and Croatia and Bosnia and Herzegovina, and the largest percentage of respondents with monthly incomes over 2,500 BAM want to travel in Europe and Croatia.

Fig. 7 Intention to travel in 2022 in the context of the current war situation between Ukraine and Russia and the number of persons in the household as a sociodemographic factor
Source: Research results, 2022.

Fig. 7 shows that, concerning the war in Ukraine, the largest percentage of respondents who live in households with 1-2 members want to travel to Europe and Bosnia and Herzegovina, while the largest percentage of respondents who live in households with 1-2 members want to travel in Croatia and Bosnia and Herzegovina, and the largest percentage of respondents who live in households with 5 or more members want to travel around Bosnia and Herzegovina and Europe.

Fig. 8 shows that, considering the war in Ukraine, the largest percentage of respondents who own a car want to travel in Europe (26.7%) and Croatia (22.5%), while the largest percentage of respondents who do not have a car want to travel in Bosnia and Herzegovina (30.8%).

Fig. 8 Intention to travel in 2022 in the context of the current war situation between Ukraine and Russia and car ownership as a sociodemographic factor
Source: Research results, 2022.

Fig. 9 Intention to travel in 2022 in the context of the current war situation between Ukraine and Russia and owning a motorcycle as a sociodemographic factor
Source: Research results, 2022.

Fig. 9 shows that, considering the war in Ukraine, the largest percentage of respondents who own a motorcycle want to travel around Europe (35.3%), while the largest percentage of respondents who do not have a motorcycle almost

Fig. 10 Intention to travel in 2022 in the context of the current war situation between Ukraine and Russia and marital status as a sociodemographic factor
Source: Research results, 2022.

Fig. 11 The intention of taking tourist trips in 2022 in the context of the current situation of the war between Russia and Ukraine
Source: Research results, 2022.

equally want to travel around Europe (22.6%), Bosnia and Herzegovina (21.8%) and Croatia (20.6%).

Fig. 10 shows that, considering the war in Ukraine, the largest percentage of single respondents want to travel to Europe, married people want to travel to Bosnia and Herzegovina and Croatia, divorced people in Croatia, and widowed people in Bosnia and Herzegovina.

Fig. 11 shows that the war between Ukraine and Russia does not have a great impact on the respondents when it comes to tourist trips, because as many as 33.2% of the respondents intend to travel the same way, while 11.7% will travel less, and 9.4% will not travel at all in 2022, in the context of the current situation of the war between Russia and Ukraine.

The non-parametric Mann-Whitney test from Table 1 shows that:

- owning a car is a statistically significant factor ($z = -1.967$, $p < 0.05$) that determines the extent to which respondents will travel in 2022 in the context of the war between Russia and Ukraine, so those respondents who own a car ($M = 138,797$) consider that they will travel more in 2022 than respondents who do not own a car ($M = 119.13$),

owning a motorcycle is a statistically significant factor ($z = -2.449$, $p < 0.05$) that determines the extent to which respondents will travel in 2022 in the context of the war between Russia and Ukraine, so those respondents who own a motorcycle ($M = 175.59$) consider that they will travel more in 2022 than respondents who do not own a motorcycle ($M = 130.09$).

The non-parametric Kruskal-Wallis test shows that in the context of the war between Russia and Ukraine:

- respondents aged 31-50 years ($M = 150.27$) statistically significantly ($z = 12.301$, $p < 0.01$) believe that they will travel more in 2022 than the oldest respondents ($M = 98.76$),
- respondents who are employed ($M = 150.49$) statistically significantly ($z = 20.068$, $p < 0.01$) believe that they will travel more in 2022 than pensioners ($M = 75.03$),
- respondents who completed postgraduate studies ($M = 162.15$) statistically significantly ($z = 11.129$, $p < 0.05$) believe that they will travel more in 2022 than respondents who completed higher school or college ($M = 123.89$),
- respondents with a monthly income between 1,500 BAM and 2,500 BAM ($M = 153.67$) statistically significantly ($z = 12.778$, $p < 0.01$) believe that they will travel more in 2022 than respondents with monthly income of less than 500 BAM ($M = 100.72$).

Tab. 1 Group statistics of the influence of socio-demographic factors on the intention to travel in 2022, in the context of the current situation of the war between Russia and Ukraine

To what extent will you travel in 2022 in the context of the current war situation between Russia and Ukraine? Group		Mean Rank	Man-Whitney Kruskal-Wallis ^b	z	p
Sex	male	140.82	7301.500 ^a	-1.274	.203
	female	128.70			
Age	18 – 30	131.49	12.301 ^b		.002
	31 – 50	150.27			
	Older than 50	98.76			
Education	Elementary School	13.00	11.129 ^b		.011
	High school	134.08			
	Associate degree or college	123.89			
	Postgraduate education	162.15			
Employment	Student	121.92	20.068 ^b		.000
	Employed	150.49			
	Pensioner	75.03			
	The rest	124.76			
Monthly household income (BAM)	Less than 500 BAM	100.72	12.778 ^b		.005
	500 BAM – 1,500 BAM	119.62			
	1,500 BAM – 2,500 BAM	153.67			
	More than 2,500 BAM	132.10			
Number of people in the household	1 - 2	145.12	3.721 ^b		.156
	3 - 4	128.76			
	5 and more	117.87			
Owning a car	YES	138.79	6211.000 ^a	-1.967	.049
	NO	119.13			
Owning a motorcycle	YES	175.59	1384.000 ^a	-2.449	.014
	NO	130.08			
Marital status	Single	135.66	1.725 ^b		.786
	Married	132.77			
	Widower/widow	105.50			
	Divorced	127.06			
	Doesn't want to answer	109.20			

Source: Research results, 2022.

Tab. 2 Which tourist destinations do you consider safer in the current war situation between Ukraine and Russia?

	Frequency	Percent
Bosnia and Herzegovina	86	32.5
Croatia	32	12.1
Serbia	2	.8
Montenegro	8	3.0
Slovenia	3	1.1
The rest of Europe	70	26.4
North America	16	6.0
South America	6	2.3
Africa	9	3.4
Australia	28	10.6
Asia	5	1.9
Total	265	100.0

Source: Research results, 2022.

From Table 2, it can be concluded that, concerning the war in Ukraine, the largest percentage of respondents believe that the safest tourist destinations are in Bosnia and Herzegovina (32.5%) and Europe (26.4%).

Tab. 3 Which means of transport will you use to travel in 2022?

	Frequency	Percent
Car	139	52.5
Bus	36	13.6
Plane	52	19.6
Boat	1	.4
I don't know/I don't want to answer	37	14.0
Total	265	100.0

Source: Research results, 2022.

Table 3 shows that the largest percentage of respondents intend to travel by car in 2022 (52.5%).

Several research questions were asked, that is, the purpose of this research.

Do socio-demographic factors influence the intention to travel in 2022 in the context of the current situation of the war between Russia and Ukraine?

From the conducted research, it can be concluded that the war between Ukraine and Russia does not have a great impact on the respondents when it comes to tourist trips, because as many as 33.2% of the respondents intend to travel as well. Aubert (2011) claims that the increase in the number of terrorist attacks, the inestimability of the international political situation, and the intensification of international conflicts only temporarily reduce tourist traffic. This conclusion was reached by Varga and Bagdi (2011) after studying the impact of attacks in various countries. This research confirms the stated results because, in 2022, the inhabitants of Bosnia and Herzegovina intend to travel to the greatest extent precisely in Europe, where the armed conflict is taking place. The study "Do socio-demographic characteristics influence destination attractiveness perceptions after political turmoil: the case of Zimbabwe?" by Woyo, Slabbert and Saayman is the first study that documented the influence of socio-demographic factors on the attractiveness of a destination in political turmoil. The most significant influential factors were the level of education and the continent of residence with four direct influences on the attractiveness of the chosen destination.

In this research, among the socio-demographic factors that influence the intention to travel in 2022, in the context of the current situation of the war between Russia and Ukraine, the following stand out as statistically significant: age, employment, education, and monthly household income. Respondents aged 31-50 believe that they will travel more in 2022 than the oldest respondents. Also, respondents who are employed believe that they will travel in 2022 more than pensioners. Education also stands out as statistically significant, because those respondents who have completed postgraduate studies believe that they will travel more in 2022 than respondents who have completed higher school or college. Respondents who have a monthly income between 1,500 BAM and 2,500 BAM believe that they will travel more in 2022 than respondents who have a monthly income of less than 500 BAM. Additionally, respondents who own a car or motorcycle will travel more in 2022 than the respondents who do not own a motorcycle or car. Numerous previous studies have confirmed that the mentioned socio-demographic factors influence the behavior of tourists (Richards, 1996; Suttikun, Chang, Acho, Ubi, Bicksler, Komolsevin and Chongsithiphol, 2018). More mobile people, who have higher monthly incomes, are employed, and have a higher level of education are more inclined to travel as tourists (Kastenholz, Carneiro and Eusébio, 2005; Wambani, Ogunjinmi, and Oladeji, 2020).

Which tourist destinations do the inhabitants of Bosnia and Herzegovina perceive as safer during the current war situation between Russia and Ukraine?

Sharifi Tarazkahi and Makan Sedaghat (2014) claim that armed conflicts can have destructive consequences on the development of countries, especially in the tourism industry. Wen, Lockyer and Zhang (2018) examined the relationship

between the image of tourist destinations and the perception of political instability by surveying 17 Chinese tourists visiting Ukraine. The survey participants pointed to political instability and the language barrier as the main risks associated with their travel to Ukraine. In a surprising twist, some tourists were drawn to risk as an element of the travel experience. The study "Political Instability Equals the Collapse of Tourism in Ukraine?" by Tomczewska-Popowycz and Quirini-Popławski (2021) shows that tourism experts from cities without well-developed tourism sectors noted that political instability has not had a direct effect on their hometowns.

In the context of the current war situation between Russia and Ukraine, respondents in this study perceive Bosnia and Herzegovina as the safest tourist destination (32.5%), followed by the rest of Europe (26.4%), Croatia (12.1%), Australia (10.6%), North America (6.0%), Africa (3.4%) and Montenegro (3%). To a lesser extent, they consider the following destinations safe: Serbia (0.8%), Slovenia (1.1%), Asia (1.9%), and South America (2.3%). From the above, it can be concluded that the respondents still perceive Europe (as a continent) the safest tourist destination, as many as 75.9% of them, which is in agreement with the aforementioned research.

Where do the people of Bosnia and Herzegovina intend to travel in the context of the current war situation between Russia and Ukraine?

Tourists mostly find it unattractive and refuse to visit countries that have problems with terrorism or have recently suffered an armed or terrorist attack. The literature generally illustrates that terror is bad for the tourism business, although in a minority of cases the impact may be small (Wolff and Larsen, 2014). The results of research conducted by Mao (2019) show that terrorism in the United Kingdom has a negative impact on British tourism, while terrorism in Europe has a positive impact on it.

This study supports the results of Mao (2019) and shows that, during 2022, and considering the war in Ukraine, the largest percentage of respondents intend to travel throughout Europe (23.4%), Bosnia and Herzegovina (21.5%) and Croatia (20.8%). As with the previous research question, the largest number of respondents intend to travel to Europe (74%). No significant differences were observed in the socio-demographic factors of the respondents in the context of the intention to travel to certain destinations. However, it was noticed that respondents with primary and secondary school mostly intend to travel in Bosnia and Herzegovina, while respondents with college and post-graduate education in the rest of Europe and North America. In 2022, pensioners intend to travel mostly in Bosnia and Herzegovina, followed by Croatia, while students and employees intend to travel in Bosnia and Herzegovina, the region, and the rest of Europe. Respondents with monthly incomes below 500 BAM will travel to Bosnia and Herzegovina and the rest of Europe in 2022, while respondents with monthly incomes between 1,500-2,500

BAM will travel to Bosnia and Herzegovina, Croatia, Montenegro, Serbia, and the rest of Europe. In 2022, respondents with 5 members or more in the household will travel the most in Bosnia and Herzegovina and the rest of Europe, and those respondents with 1-2 members in the rest of Europe. Those respondents who own a car intend to travel to the rest of Europe and Croatia in 2022, while those respondents who do not own a car will travel to Bosnia and Herzegovina and Croatia. Respondents who own a motorcycle will, to the greatest extent, travel around the rest of Europe in the context of the current war situation between Russia and Ukraine. Married respondents plan to travel in Bosnia and Herzegovina and Croatia, widowed respondents mostly in Bosnia and Herzegovina, and divorced respondents in Croatia.

What means of transport will be used for tourist trips in the context of the current war situation between Russia and Ukraine?

It can be said that politics is a management mechanism, which has the power to ensure political stability. However, peace in the country depends on the political culture and economic power holders. For example, in 2005, anti-government demonstrators, known as "yellow vests", stormed the terminal building of Suvarnabhumi Airport in Thailand and a fight broke out with airport officials. In the interest of passenger safety, the authorities closed the airport. Thousands of airline passengers were stranded due to political instability (Ingram, Tabari and Watthanakhomprathip, 2013). Previously conducted research has shown that travelers in crises such as armed conflicts, terrorism, and the Covid-19 pandemic are more inclined to use a car as a means of transport for tourist trips (Habib and Anik, 2021; Hrelja and Rye, 2022).

In this study, over half of the respondents (52.5%) intend to travel by car in 2022 in the context of the current war situation between Russia and Ukraine. To a lesser extent, respondents plan to travel by plane (19.6%), 13.6% by bus, and only 0.4% of respondents plan to travel by boat in 2022.

CONCLUSIONS

Wars in different regions have different impacts on tourism. The reason for this may come from the different images of the continents. As a result, the impact of the armed conflict between Russia and Ukraine does not have a major impact on the demand for tourist destinations in Europe. The results of this research can be used as a theoretical basis for policy-making within Europe.

This research determines if there is a connection between war and tourism and if there is any relationship between them. In fact, many factors influence tourism, such as socio-demographic factors. Among the socio-demographic factors that influence the intention to travel in 2022, this research highlights the following: age, employment, education, and monthly household income. Research studies

on the causal relationship between socio-demographic variables and destination attractiveness are limited to destinations with numerous political challenges, such as wars, terrorism, and political turmoil, and therefore further research is needed.

This study explains the hypothesized relationships only in a short period and in a certain period. In the future, studies related to tourism and armed conflict should collect data over a longitudinal period to observe changes in international tourism behavior.

The first limitation of the research is that it uses a convenience sample with 265 respondents. Another limitation of the research is that the results can only be applied to Bosnia and Herzegovina. Although Bosnia and Herzegovina is in Europe, it is quite geographically distant from Ukraine and the armed conflict with Russia.

Recommendations for further research are that this kind of research should be carried out in other European countries as well, as well as that other conflicts (wars, terrorist attacks, as well as other political conflicts in the world) should be included in the research, and not just one specific armed conflict, such as the war between Russia and Ukraine. It is also recommended that the sample be much larger because then the relevance of the results is greater. Future research could also focus on the effects of political instability on various forms of tourism in a regional sense.

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